

An Augustinian take: The loves of the mathematics education research community

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Psychoanalytic research in mathematics education focuses on the unconscious narratives in the field with a predominant focus on desire and its derivatives. Yet, over a millennium ago, Augustine of Hippo addressed similar themes with his concept of love and his definition of a community. In this project presentation, I argue that Augustine’s notion of love as craving and his definition of a community can inform research efforts in mathematics education in an original way. Namely, I will use Augustine’s work to help identify potential loves of the field and discuss how those loves subsequently shape the field and its research.

Introduction

There has been a recent uptake of psychoanalysis for research purposes in mathematics education (see the work of Alexandre Pais, Tony Brown, Tamara Bibby, etc.). In the introduction to the book *The Psychology of Mathematics Education: A Psychoanalytic Displacement*, Tony Brown, of Manchester Metropolitan University and the editor of the book, discusses how psychoanalysis entered the scene of mathematics education research. He describes how there was a shift away from traditional psychology towards “a psychology understood more through relations between people” (Brown, 2008, p. 1). Much of this initial work used Lacan’s theories to promote “the shift from bio-scientific to narrative emphases in interpreting Freud’s work” (p. 3) and is focused on what Lacan called “the truth of desire” (Lacan, 2019). Thus, psychoanalytic research in mathematics education attempts to identify subconscious or unconscious narratives in the field that often depend on desire.

Approximately 1,650 years ago, however, Augustine of Hippo discussed themes of desire and the role of desire in communities. Adjusting a definition from Cicero, Augustine (2009) wrote:

[...] for example, if one should say, ‘A people is the association of a multitude of rational beings united by a common agreement on the objects of their love,’ then it follows that to observe the character of a particular people we must examine the objects of its love. (§ 19.24)

For Augustine, “love is indeed nothing else than to crave something for its own sake” and “a kind of motion, and all motion is toward something” (as cited in Arendt et al., p.9). This elevation of love (as craving, or desire) shares similarities with some of the work in psychoanalysis. Thus, while I do not intend to diminish the work of psychoanalysts in

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mathematics education research, I'd like to offer an Augustinian "take" on mathematics education research and suggest that this ancient North African bishop can inform our work in an original and profound fashion—meaning, I'd like to use Augustine's conception of love as an opportunity to address the mathematics education research community's loves. This presentation reports the initial findings of an ongoing project where I attempt to answer two questions: first, what are the field's loves? And second, how do those loves shape and form the field and its research?

Before continuing, I think it is important to note that I am not suggesting a theological analysis of the field. As Hannah Arendt demonstrated in the field of political theory, Augustine's work extends beyond theology and Christian doctrine. Arendt thought that, regardless of culture, religion, or worldview, it was relevant that humans are first and foremost lovers. Arendt (1996) even suggested that, "Strictly speaking, he who does not love and desire at all is a nobody" (p. 18).

Arendt felt so strongly about Augustine's conception of love, she wrote her doctoral dissertation on the subject (entitled *Love and Saint Augustine*) and spent the remainder of her life refining and editing the work (Arendt et al., 1996). The lifelong work on her dissertation reflects her love of Augustine, demonstrates his influence on her work, and highlights how highly she thought of her original research question regarding "the relevance of the neighbor" (p. x). She explored Augustine's conception of love in order to study the phenomena of "neighbor" and, as Arendt explains, "to understand in what sense our neighbor is loved in adhering to the commandment of neighborly love" (p. 7).

Augustine's concept of love

Augustine distinguishes between two different types of love: *caritas* and *cupiditas*. For Augustine, *cupiditas* is love with a wrong object and *caritas* is love with a right object. Augustine's definitions of "wrong" and "right" are, of course, grounded in Christianity. But, as Arendt (1996) points out, "both right and wrong love (*caritas* and *cupiditas*) have this in common – craving desire, that is, *appetitus*. Hence, Augustine warns, 'Love, but be careful what you love.'" (p. 17).

Augustine offers this warning because he believes a person or communities' loves are central to who they are. Arendt writes,

Desire mediates between subject and object, and it annihilates the distance between them by transforming the subject into a lover and the object into the beloved. For the lover is never isolated from what he loves; he belongs to it. (p. 18)

This close intimacy – this binding – of the lover and the beloved is defining for the lover. The stronger the love, the more intimate the union with the beloved. Augustine (as cited in Arendt et al., 1996, p. 18) writes, "Such is each as is his love." Arendt (1996) describes how Augustine uses the word *inhaerere*, which is translated as "clinging to," to denote the closeness of lover and beloved. Commenting on this theme of Augustine, she writes, "Happiness is achieved only when the beloved becomes a permanently inherent element of one's own being" (p. 19).

Arendt (1996) also highlights that, “A thing is sought for its own sake (in *caritas* or *cupiditas*) if its possession puts desire to rest. Thus, nothing can be said to be “loved” which is sought for the sake of something else” (p. 32). Which begs the question: what are the mathematics education research community’s loves?

Science, our first love

In this presentation of my ongoing attempt to operationalize Augustine’s concept of love, I’d like to suggest that the scientific paradigm is a core love of the mathematics education research community and describe how it can warp our field. Ernest (1998) describes scientific research in mathematics education as being founded on

rationalism and the scientific method as employed in the physical sciences, experimental psychology, etc. It is concerned with objectivity, prediction, replicability, and the discovery of scientific generalizations or laws describing the phenomena in question. (p. 77)

Ernest goes on to describe two other major research paradigms: the interpretive, which for Ernest (1998) has to do with “understanding, interpretation, intersubjectivity, [and] lived truth” (p. 77), and the critical-theoretic, which aims for social and institutional change through social critique. He argues that each respective paradigm plays a role in the mathematics education research community, that no paradigm should be put on a pedestal, and that antagonistic attacks against entire paradigms should be discouraged.

Yet the scientific paradigm’s strong grip on the field as a whole has ramifications for the field per Augustine’s notion of love. Prominent researchers (e.g., Cobb, 2007; von Glasersfeld & Steffe, 1991) that work in the interpretive paradigm still frame the field as a science. Consequently, while many of these researchers assent to pragmatist notions of truth and meaning, they function within remnants of the scientific paradigm. This continued worship of the scientific paradigm has led to a scientism that looms large over the field. Thus, I argue that science is the object of the majority of the field’s love and is sought for its own sake.

Per Augustine, I argue that this love is *cupiditas* and must be critiqued. While Ernest (2012) recognizes the consequences of adopting certain theories, he seemingly overlooks the consequences of having the scientific paradigm as a core love of the field. Yet the scientific paradigm distorts the field as a whole and skews the field’s conception of knowledge. Anzaldúa (1987) identifies a major consequence of scientism. She writes,

In trying to become “objective,” Western culture made “objects” of things and people when it distanced itself from them, thereby losing “touch” with them. (p. 59)

Anzaldúa’s description of the consequences of the West’s pursuit of objectivity is precisely what is occurring within mathematics education research community today. In Augustinian fashion, Anzaldúa explains that the pursuit of objectivity ultimately leads to dehumanization. While researchers within the interpretive tradition reject the idea that knowledge reflects an objective, ontological reality (Ulrich et al., 2014), they also embrace obvious expressions of scientism. For example, Campbell (2020) suggests that soon we will be able to equip students to wear caps that transmit “high spatial and temporal resolution

EEG or MEG signals” (p. 99) to a central console that can then be analysed by their teacher in real time. Yet, per Anzaldúa, is there anything more distancing and dehumanizing? Where are the affections in such a cold, imagined future? For a field predominantly concerned with human beings, the scientific paradigm and scientism should not be objects of the mathematics education research community’s love.

Concluding thoughts

In this project presentation, I argued that Augustine’s notion of love can help diagnose the ills of the mathematics education research community. I then briefly excavated and examined the field’s love of the scientific paradigm. In the future, further loves need to be explored as psychoanalytic research has already identified the field’s love of capital (Pais, 2014). Ultimately, the mathematics education research community needs an imaginative overhaul. The field remains captive to unworthy loves and these objects of love continue to warp the field as a whole.

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